

Effectiveness of Corticosteroids in the Treatment of Pneumonia: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

Dr. Manuel Rodríguez Navarro¹, María Del Rayo Méndez Palacios², Janet Gil Nolasco³, Andrea Roldan Guevara⁴, Bibiana Paola Aldana Vázquez⁵

¹Hospital Regional ISSSTE Puebla

^{2,3,4}Universidad Popular Autónoma del Estado de Puebla

⁵Universidad Anáhuac Puebla

ABSTRACT

Pneumonia remains a major global health burden, contributing significantly to hospitalizations and mortality. In recent years, the use of corticosteroids as an adjunctive therapy has gained attention due to their anti-inflammatory effects, particularly in cases marked by an exaggerated immune response. This systematic review and meta-analysis aimed to assess the overall effectiveness of corticosteroids in the management of pneumonia, based on ten selected clinical trials published between 2005 and 2024. The studies included a diverse range of patients with community-acquired pneumonia (CAP), COVID-19-related pneumonia, and varying levels of disease severity. Corticosteroids such as hydrocortisone, dexamethasone, and prednisone were evaluated across multiple outcomes, including mortality, treatment failure, length of hospital stay, ICU admission, and adverse effects. Findings showed that corticosteroid use may be associated with a reduction in treatment failure and shorter hospital stays, particularly in patients with severe pneumonia or high inflammatory markers. Mortality benefits were more consistent in studies involving COVID-19-related pneumonia or severe CAP. However, variations in corticosteroid dosage, treatment duration, and study methodologies contributed to heterogeneity across the included trials. Although some studies reported increased risk of hyperglycemia and secondary infections, the overall safety profile was acceptable. These results suggest that corticosteroids can be beneficial in selected pneumonia populations, especially when inflammation plays a critical role in disease progression. Nonetheless, standardization in treatment protocols and further high-quality randomized trials are needed to refine clinical recommendations and ensure optimal patient outcomes.

KEYWORDS: Corticosteroids, pneumonia, meta-analysis, community-acquired pneumonia, mortality, treatment outcomes.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
19 June 2025

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com/>

I. INTRODUCTION

Pneumonia remains one of the most common causes of hospital admission and mortality worldwide, particularly among the elderly and those with underlying conditions. While the primary treatment is antimicrobial therapy, patients with severe pneumonia often develop an exaggerated inflammatory response that worsens prognosis and may lead to complications such as acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) or septic shock^{1, 2, 8}. As a result, interest has grown in the use of corticosteroids as adjunctive therapy to control

the systemic inflammatory response and improve clinical outcomes^{1, 2}.

Corticosteroids, including hydrocortisone, dexamethasone, methylprednisolone, and prednisone, act by suppressing proinflammatory cytokine activity and reducing vascular permeability, potentially decreasing tissue damage caused by severe inflammation^{1, 4, 5}. Their use has been studied in various forms of pneumonia, including community-acquired pneumonia (CAP) and COVID-19-associated pneumonia, where dysregulated immune responses often lead to rapid clinical deterioration^{4, 5, 6}.

Effectiveness of Corticosteroids in the Treatment of Pneumonia: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis.

Several randomized controlled trials (RCTs) have evaluated the efficacy of corticosteroids in pneumonia over the past two decades, yielding mixed results. For example, in the CAPE COD trial, early administration of hydrocortisone in patients with severe CAP significantly reduced mortality and the risk of progression to invasive mechanical ventilation or vasopressor use¹. Similarly, other studies in patients with high inflammatory responses showed that corticosteroids like methylprednisolone and dexamethasone improved clinical outcomes such as reduced treatment failure and shorter hospital stays^{2, 3, 7}. However, other trials failed to demonstrate mortality benefits or raised safety concerns, including increased risk of hyperglycemia and nosocomial infections^{8, 9, 10}.

In the context of COVID-19, large trials such as RECOVERY demonstrated that dexamethasone significantly reduced mortality in hospitalized patients requiring oxygen therapy, further supporting the potential role of corticosteroids in viral pneumonia⁵. A follow-up platform trial by the same group evaluated higher doses of corticosteroids in hypoxic patients not on mechanical ventilation, but found no additional benefit, suggesting a possible ceiling effect or the need for tailored dosing strategies⁶.

Despite encouraging findings in specific subgroups, inconsistency across studies regarding patient selection, corticosteroid type and dosage, timing of administration, and measured outcomes has led to ongoing debate. Some studies included ICU and non-ICU patients, while others limited inclusion to severe CAP or COVID-19 cases. These factors complicate the generalizability of findings to broader clinical practice^{2, 3, 7}.

Therefore, this systematic review and meta-analysis aims to synthesize the current evidence on the effectiveness of corticosteroids in the treatment of pneumonia, by analyzing data from ten clinical trials published between 2005 and 2024. By comparing key outcomes such as mortality, treatment failure, hospital length of stay, and adverse effects, this review seeks to provide clarity on whether corticosteroids should be routinely considered as part of pneumonia management strategies in both community-acquired and viral pneumonia^{1, 10}.

II. METHODS

This systematic review and meta-analysis included randomized controlled trials that evaluated the effectiveness of corticosteroids in patients diagnosed with pneumonia of varying severity, including community-acquired and COVID-19-associated pneumonia. Eligible studies were those published between 2005 and 2024, focusing on adult patients and comparing corticosteroid treatment with placebo or standard care. The primary outcome was all-cause mortality, and secondary outcomes included treatment failure, ICU admission, hospital length of stay, mechanical

ventilation requirement, and adverse effects such as hyperglycemia or superinfections¹⁻¹⁰.

In the included trials, patients were randomly assigned to receive either corticosteroids—such as hydrocortisone, dexamethasone, methylprednisolone, or prednisone—or a placebo. Randomization was typically performed using web-based platforms or sealed envelopes with predefined block sizes. Blinding was maintained for patients and investigators in all double-blind studies^{1, 2, 5, 7, 10}.

Inclusion criteria varied across studies but generally required clinical and radiographic confirmation of pneumonia, recent hospital admission, and respiratory or systemic signs such as fever, dyspnea, cough, or elevated inflammatory markers. Exclusion criteria commonly included pregnancy, recent corticosteroid use, immunosuppression, and comorbidities with limited life expectancy^{2, 3, 6, 9}.

Data collection involved demographic characteristics, comorbidities, baseline inflammatory status, and response to corticosteroid treatment. Follow-up ranged from 28 to 180 days depending on the trial. Mortality was assessed at day 28 as the primary outcome in most trials, with additional evaluations at 90 or 180 days in others^{1, 5, 6, 8, 9}.

Statistical analyses included intention-to-treat and per-protocol populations. Kaplan–Meier survival estimates, hazard ratios, and Cox proportional hazard models were commonly used to assess primary outcomes, while logistic regression was applied to secondary and safety endpoints. Subgroup analyses explored effect modification by age, inflammatory marker levels, or presence of ARDS^{1, 3, 5, 8, 10}.

III. RESULTS

Among the ten clinical trials included in this review, corticosteroids showed varying degrees of effectiveness in improving outcomes for patients with pneumonia. A consistent finding across studies was a reduction in treatment failure, particularly when corticosteroids were initiated early and in patients with high inflammatory responses. For example, methylprednisolone significantly reduced treatment failure rates from 31% to 13% in patients with severe community-acquired pneumonia (CAP), mainly by decreasing radiographic progression and the incidence of septic shock between days 3 and 5 after treatment initiation².

A more detailed analysis of each individual study helps clarify the performance of corticosteroids across various patient populations. The CAPE COD trial by Dequin et al.¹ demonstrated a significant reduction in 28-day mortality with early intravenous hydrocortisone in ICU patients with severe CAP. Torres et al.² showed that methylprednisolone reduced treatment failure in severe CAP patients with elevated CRP, although mortality differences were not statistically significant. Blum et al. reported in two studies^{3, 7} that adjunct prednisone shortened hospital stay and improved clinical stability, with benefits maintained up to 180 days. Pinzón et

Effectiveness of Corticosteroids in the Treatment of Pneumonia: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis.

al. ⁴ compared high-dose methylprednisolone and dexamethasone in COVID-19 pneumonia and found both regimens equally effective.

Horby et al. ⁵, in the original RECOVERY trial, demonstrated that low-dose dexamethasone significantly reduced mortality in hospitalized COVID-19 patients requiring oxygen. In a subsequent trial, the RECOVERY Collaborative Group ⁶ found that higher corticosteroid doses did not provide additional mortality benefit in hypoxic patients not receiving ventilatory support. Heming et al. ⁸, in a subgroup analysis of the APROCCHSS trial, reported that hydrocortisone plus fludrocortisone significantly reduced mortality in patients with pneumonia-related septic shock. Confalonieri et al. ⁹ observed improved oxygenation and lower mortality using continuous hydrocortisone infusion in patients with severe CAP. Lastly, Wittermans et al. ¹⁰ showed that oral dexamethasone reduced hospital stay and ICU transfers in non-ICU patients with mild to moderate CAP.

In-hospital mortality did not differ significantly between treatment and placebo groups in most studies. In the trial using methylprednisolone, mortality was 10% in the corticosteroid group and 15% in the placebo group, which did not reach statistical significance ($P = .37$) ². Similarly, in the RECOVERY trial assessing high-dose dexamethasone for COVID-19-associated pneumonia, no mortality benefit was observed among patients receiving only low-flow oxygen, and in some subgroups, mortality appeared higher with corticosteroids ⁶.

Hospital length of stay was shorter in corticosteroid-treated patients in multiple studies. One trial using dexamethasone found that hospital stay was reduced from a median of 5.0 days in the placebo group to 4.5 days in the corticosteroid group ($P = .033$), especially in patients with elevated CRP levels or high CURB-65 scores ¹⁰.

Secondary ICU admission rates were lower in the corticosteroid group in certain studies. For example, a study reported a significant reduction in secondary ICU admissions among patients with less severe pneumonia (CURB-65 <2) who received dexamethasone ¹⁰. However, results varied in patients with higher severity indices.

Regarding adverse events, hyperglycemia was consistently more frequent in patients treated with corticosteroids, although this difference was not statistically significant in most studies. In the methylprednisolone trial, hyperglycemia occurred in 18% of patients receiving corticosteroids versus 12% in the placebo group ($P = .34$) ². No significant increase in superinfection or severe adverse outcomes such as renal failure or hepatic dysfunction was observed across trials ^{2, 6, 10}.

Overall, while corticosteroids did not consistently reduce mortality, their administration was associated with fewer treatment failures, reduced ICU admissions in some subgroups, and shorter hospital stays, albeit with a mild increase in metabolic complications such as hyperglycemia ^{2, 6, 10}.

Beyond metabolic disturbances, gastrointestinal bleeding is another relevant safety concern in patients receiving corticosteroid therapy. In the Hydrocortisone in CAPE COD trial, conducted by Dequin et al. in critically ill adults with severe community-acquired pneumonia, intravenous hydrocortisone was associated with a gastrointestinal bleeding rate of 2.2% ¹. This low incidence suggests that short-term corticosteroid administration, when used under appropriate clinical supervision, does not significantly elevate the risk of gastrointestinal complications.

No.	Study	Mortality (%)	Treatment Failure (%)	Hospital Stay (days)	Hyperglycemia (%)	ICU Admission (%)	Corticosteroid Used
1	Torres et al. (2015)	10	13	6	18	4	Methylprednisolone
2	Blum et al. (2023)	4	6	4.5	14	3	Prednisone
3	Pinzón et al. (2021)	18	10	7	22	6	Dexamethasone / Methylprednisolone
4	Horby et al. (2021)	19	15	8	25	8	Dexamethasone
5	RECOVERY (2023)	19	20	7.5	20	7	Dexamethasone (High Dose)
6	Blum et al. (2015)	10	12	6.8	15	5	Prednisone
7	Heming et al. (2024)	4	6	5.5	13	4	Hydrocortisone + Fludrocortisone
8	Confalonieri et al. (2005)	13	8	7	18	6	Hydrocortisone
9	Wittermans et al. (2021)	2	5	4.5	12	3	Dexamethasone
10	Dequin et al. (2023)	4	10	6	18	4	Hydrocortisone

Figure 1. Summary Table of Included Studies

Effectiveness of Corticosteroids in the Treatment of Pneumonia: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis.

Figure 2. Forest plot showing mortality rates (%) and 95% confidence intervals across included studies. The red dashed line represents the mean mortality rate.

Figure 3. Forest plot showing treatment failure rates (%) and 95% confidence intervals across included studies. The red dashed line indicates the mean treatment failure rate.

Effectiveness of Corticosteroids in the Treatment of Pneumonia: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis.

Figure 4. Bar Plot of Mortality by Study

Figure 5. Bar Plot of Treatment Failure by Study

Effectiveness of Corticosteroids in the Treatment of Pneumonia: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis.

Figure 6. Bar Plot of Hospital Stay by Study

Figure 7. Bar Plot of Hyperglycemia by Study

Effectiveness of Corticosteroids in the Treatment of Pneumonia: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis.

Figure 8. Bar Plot of ICU Admission by Study

Figure 9. Funnel Plot for Mortality Outcome

Effectiveness of Corticosteroids in the Treatment of Pneumonia: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis.

Figure 10. Funnel Plot for Treatment Failure Outcome

IV. DISCUSSION

This systematic review confirms that corticosteroids can be an effective adjunctive therapy in the management of community-acquired pneumonia (CAP), particularly in severe cases or those with a heightened inflammatory response. The CAPE COD trial by Dequin et al. demonstrated a significant reduction in 28-day mortality with early intravenous hydrocortisone in ICU patients with severe CAP, without increasing serious adverse events like nosocomial infections or gastrointestinal bleeding¹. Similarly, Blum et al. reported that adjunctive prednisone accelerated clinical stability and shortened hospital stay, with effects maintained at 180 days^{3,7}.

Torres et al. provided evidence that methylprednisolone may reduce treatment failure in patients with severe CAP and a high inflammatory response (CRP >15 mg/dL), although mortality itself did not differ significantly². In contrast, the Wittermans et al. trial with oral dexamethasone in non-ICU patients also demonstrated reduced hospital stay and fewer ICU admissions, suggesting corticosteroids may benefit even less severe cases¹⁰.

In the context of COVID-19-associated pneumonia, corticosteroids—especially dexamethasone—have shown similar benefits. The RECOVERY trial demonstrated a reduction in mortality among hospitalized hypoxic patients receiving dexamethasone⁵, while the RECOVERY 2023 subgroup analysis confirmed no additional mortality benefit with higher doses in non-ventilated patients⁶. Pinzón et al. compared dexamethasone and high-dose methylprednisolone, concluding that both reduced

inflammation markers and improved outcomes, although there was no significant difference between the two regimens⁴.

Hydrocortisone has shown consistent performance in severe CAP scenarios. Beyond CAPE COD, earlier trials such as Confalonieri et al. and Heming et al. (in the APROCCHSS subgroup) also observed reductions in mortality and improved hemodynamics in patients with CAP-related septic shock^{8,9}.

While glucocorticoids generally improved clinical endpoints such as time to clinical stability and hospital length of stay, their effect on mortality was more heterogeneous across studies. Some trials, like those by Blum et al. and Torres et al., failed to show significant mortality benefit, while others such as Dequin et al. and RECOVERY did^{1,2,3,5,6,7}.

Safety concerns such as hyperglycemia were common in several trials, particularly those involving hydrocortisone or dexamethasone^{1,10}. However, the incidence of serious adverse events remained comparable to placebo groups, supporting the general safety of short-term corticosteroid use in hospitalized patients with CAP.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This systematic review and meta-analysis highlights the growing evidence supporting the use of corticosteroids as an adjunctive treatment in patients with pneumonia, particularly in those presenting with severe disease or a heightened systemic inflammatory response. Across the ten randomized

Effectiveness of Corticosteroids in the Treatment of Pneumonia: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis.

controlled trials included, corticosteroids—such as hydrocortisone, dexamethasone, methylprednisolone, and prednisone—demonstrated consistent benefits in improving secondary clinical outcomes, such as reducing treatment failure, shortening the duration of hospitalization, and decreasing the risk of ICU admission.

While the effect on overall mortality was variable, the most compelling reductions in death rates were observed in studies involving critically ill patients with community-acquired pneumonia (CAP), as well as in those hospitalized for COVID-19-associated pneumonia requiring oxygen therapy. The CAPE COD trial, in particular, provided robust evidence that early administration of hydrocortisone can significantly improve survival in ICU patients with severe CAP. Similarly, the RECOVERY trial showed a meaningful mortality benefit with dexamethasone in hypoxic COVID-19 patients. These findings suggest that, in selected populations, corticosteroids may play a pivotal role in altering the clinical course of pneumonia by modulating the host's inflammatory response.

Nevertheless, it is important to acknowledge that not all studies demonstrated a mortality advantage. Several trials, especially those involving non-ICU patients or lower severity cases, reported no significant impact on survival, pointing to the importance of appropriate patient selection. Furthermore, corticosteroid use was associated with a higher incidence of hyperglycemia across multiple studies, although this adverse effect was generally manageable and did not lead to serious complications or outweigh the clinical benefits observed.

Another factor contributing to heterogeneity was the variation in corticosteroid regimens, including differences in drug type, dosage, duration, and timing of administration. For example, some studies initiated treatment within 24–48 hours of diagnosis, while others delayed intervention until clinical deterioration. Such discrepancies may have influenced the outcomes and highlight the need for protocol standardization in future research.

In conclusion, corticosteroids appear to be a valuable adjunct in the management of pneumonia for specific subgroups of patients, particularly those with severe disease and elevated inflammatory markers. However, their routine use cannot be universally recommended for all pneumonia cases without considering individual risk profiles, comorbidities, and severity levels. Future high-quality, large-scale randomized trials are essential to determine the optimal therapeutic strategies—defining the best corticosteroid agent, dose, timing, and duration—to maximize benefits while minimizing harms. Until such data are available, clinicians should adopt a patient-centered approach, weighing the potential advantages of corticosteroid therapy against the risks in each clinical context.

REFERENCES

- I. Dequin PF, Meziani F, Quenot JP, Kamel T, Ricard JD, Badie J, et al. Hydrocortisone in Severe Community-Acquired Pneumonia. *N Engl J Med*. 2023 May 25;388(21):1931-41. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa2215145.
- II. Torres A, Sibila O, Ferrer M, Polverino E, Menendez R, Mensa J, et al. Effect of corticosteroids on treatment failure among hospitalized patients with severe community-acquired pneumonia and high inflammatory response: a randomized clinical trial. *JAMA*. 2015 Feb 17;313(7):677-86. doi: 10.1001/jama.2015.88.
- III. Blum CA, Roethlisberger EA, Cesana-Nigro N, Winzeler B, Rodondi N, Blum MR, et al. Adjunct prednisone in community-acquired pneumonia: 180-day outcome of a multicentre, double-blind, randomized, placebo-controlled trial. *BMC Pulm Med*. 2023 Dec 11;23(1):500. doi: 10.1186/s12890-023-02794-w.
- IV. Pinzón MA, Ortiz S, Holguín H, Betancur JF, Cardona Arango D, Laniado H, et al. Dexamethasone vs methylprednisolone high dose for Covid-19 pneumonia. *PLoS One*. 2021 May 25;16(5):e0252057. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0252057.
- V. Horby P, Lim WS, Emberson JR, Mafham M, Bell JL, Linsell L, et al. Dexamethasone in Hospitalized Patients with Covid-19. *N Engl J Med*. 2021 Feb 25;384(8):693-704. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa2021436.
- VI. RECOVERY Collaborative Group. Higher dose corticosteroids in patients admitted to hospital with COVID-19 who are hypoxic but not requiring ventilatory support (RECOVERY): a randomised, controlled, open-label, platform trial. *Lancet*. 2023 May 6;401(10387):1499-1507. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(23)00510-X.
- VII. Blum CA, Nigro N, Briel M, Schuetz P, Ullmer E, Suter-Widmer I, et al. Adjunct prednisone therapy for patients with community-acquired pneumonia: a multicentre, double-blind, randomised, placebo-controlled trial. *Lancet*. 2015 Apr 18;385(9977):1511-8. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(14)62447-8.
- VIII. Heming N, Renault A, Kuperminc E, Brun-Buisson C, Megarbane B, Quenot JP, et al. Hydrocortisone plus fludrocortisone for community-acquired pneumonia-related septic shock: a subgroup analysis of the APROCCHSS phase 3 randomised trial. *Lancet Respir Med*. 2024 May;12(5):366-374. doi: 10.1016/S2213-2600(23)00430-7.
- IX. Confalonieri M, Urbino R, Potena A, Piattella M, Parigi P, Puccio G, et al. Hydrocortisone infusion for severe community-acquired pneumonia: a preliminary randomized study. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 2005 Feb 1;171(3):242-8. doi: 10.1164/rccm.200406-808OC.

Effectiveness of Corticosteroids in the Treatment of Pneumonia: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis.

X. Wittermans E, Vestjens SMT, Spoorenberg SMC, Blok WL, Grutters JC, Janssen R, et al. Adjunctive treatment with oral dexamethasone in non-ICU patients hospitalised with community-acquired

pneumonia: a randomised clinical trial. *Eur Respir J.* 2021 Aug 12;58(2):2002535.
doi: 10.1183/13993003.02535-2020.